

Economic Empowerment of Women through Government Schemes: A Study

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Introduction

Empowerment is a way to defy challenges and overcome barriers in life. It is the means through which people increase their ability to shape their lives and environment. It also implies a state of mind or the attitude of a person. It is an active process enabling women to realize their full potential and power in all spheres of life. Many social, economic, political and cultural barriers retard the growth of women entrepreneurship. It requires courage, firm attitude and an inherent desire for women to become successful entrepreneurs. Women should possess persistence and firm determination to succeed in their venture. Entrepreneurship is a way to attain self-awareness, self-respect, self-determination and self-confidence. In this article, an attempt has been made to know how entrepreneurship has been a source of women empowerment. In other words, the present study aims to understand the extent to which entrepreneurship contributes towards women empowerment. The analysis has been made from various angles such as improvement in educational status; training programmes undergone; independence in family, financial, economic and social activities; increase in family income and standard of living; awareness of the value of nutritional diet; ability to take decisions; participation in public activities; and increase in self-confidence.

Parameters of Empowerment

Undoubtedly entrepreneurship contributes significantly for empowerment of Women Entrepreneurship itself has various Parameters of empowering women. The following analysis is aimed at to ascertain how these different parameters have contributed in empowering women in the study area.

Level of Education

One of the main factors contributing to women empowerment is improvement in the level of education. It is to be studied as to whether entrepreneurship has induced the women to acquire higher qualification after entering business. Analysing the improvement in the educational qualification of women entrepreneurs can throw light on its impact on empowerment. It can be observed that in manufacturing units, 68.06 percent of urban and 59.46 percent of rural women have improved their educational qualifications after becoming entrepreneurs (see Table 1). In service units, 57.78 percent of urban and 62.25 percent of rural women entrepreneurs have increased their educational qualification. In general, 63.04 per cent of urban and 61.15 per cent of rural women have improved their education qualifications after becoming entrepreneurs. The overall increase in educational qualifications is 62.06 percent. It can be concluded that the entrepreneurship has led to improvement in the educational qualifications of the respondents and thus their knowledge base to manage their unity successfully.

Table 1 Improvement in the Level of Education of Sample Women After becoming Entrepreneurs

Level of Education	Manufacturing		Service		Total	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
Increased	49 (68.06)	44 (59.46)	38 (57.58)	52 (62.25)	87 (63.04)	96 (61.15)
Not Increased	23 (31.94)	30 (40.54)	28 (42.42)	31 (37.35)	51 (36.96)	61 (38.85)
Total	72 (100)	74 (100)	66 (100)	83 (100)	138 (100)	157 (100)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate the percentage to total.

Source: Sample survey.

Participation in training Programmes

The technological up-gradation necessitates people to be trained for skill development. In order to cope up with the rapid changes in the requirements of skill and knowledge, the need for systematic training has been felt in all fields of business activity. Training enables entrepreneurs to get acquainted with the task and improve their skills and knowledge. Even for experienced women entrepreneurs, training in technical, managerial, marketing fields is necessary to reorient and enable them to cope up with new techniques. Skill acquisition through training is considered as a source of women empowerment. It can be observed that in urban manufacturing units, 70.83 per cent of sample women entrepreneurs have undergone technical training, 9.72 per cent managerial, 11.11 per cent marketing, 20.78 per cent other fields and the rest have not undergone any training (see table 2). In the case of rural manufacturing units, 85.14 per cent have undergone training, while the remaining had no training. In service units 12.12 percent of urban and 22.89 per cent of rural entrepreneurs have not under gone any training. On an overall evaluation, it can be inferred that training is more popular with urban women entrepreneurs as compared to rural entrepreneurs. Further, the proportion of entrepreneurs who have undergone training from manufacturing sector is higher than that of service sector. Further, more, entrepreneurs who are provided technical training out number the rest. Imparting of training improves the level of skill and knowledge, which may be considered as a source empowerment. It can, therefore, safely be concluded that entrepreneurship played a catalyst role in empowerment of women.

Table 2 Participation in Training Programmes by Sample Women Entrepreneurs

Training	Manufacturing		Service		Total	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
Technical	51 (70.83)	56 (75.68)	15 (22.73)	28 (33.72)	66 (47.53)	84 (53.50)
Managerial	7 (9.72)	5 (6.76)	22 (33.33)	20 (24.10)	29 (21.01)	25 (15.93)
Marketing	8 (11.11)	1 (1.35)	19 (28.79)	12 (14.46)	27 (19.57)	13 (8.28)
Other fields	2 (2.78)	1 (1.35)	2 (3.03)	4 (4.82)	4 (2.90)	5 (3.18)
No training	4 (5.56)	11 (14.86)	8 (12.12)	19 (22.89)	12 (8.70)	30 (19.11)
Total	72 (100)	74 (100)	66 (100)	83 (100)	138 (100)	157 (100)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate the percentage to total.

Source: Sample survey.

Capacity to Mobilise Funds

Economic empowerment of women can be judged by their ability to mobilise the required funds. It is evident from an analysis of contents of Table 2 that in the case of manufacturing units, 18.06 per cent of urban and 8.11 per cent of rural entrepreneurs met their fund requirements from their own source; 12.50 per cent of urban and 18.92 percent of rural entrepreneurs met from family funds; 52.70 per cent of rural and 40.28 per cent of urban entrepreneurs mobilized funds from banks; 19.44 per cent of urban and 9.46 per cent of rural entrepreneurs procured the funds from friends; 4.17 per cent of urban and 6.76 per cent of rural entrepreneurs mobilised funds through money-lenders and the remaining from other sources. In the case of service units, 15.15 per cent of urban and 13.2 per cent of rural entrepreneurs met their financial requirements from their own funds; 40.91 per cent of urban and 19.28 percent of rural entrepreneurs through their family funds; 24.24 per cent of urban and 56.63 per cent of rural entrepreneurs managed through bank loans and the rest through friends, money-lenders and others. There is a significant difference in the method of raising funds between urban and rural respondents. This is revealed by the fact that the calculated value of chi-square at 5 d.f is 15.188 which is significant (table value 11.070) at 5 percent level. It may be inferred that the method of raising funds by women entrepreneurs is not the same in urban and rural areas. When all the sample entrepreneurs are put together, 22.37 per cent depend on their family funds and the rest from other means. A significant proportion of entrepreneurs raise funds from banks. It is a clear proof of financial independence and the ability to raise funds on their own. It may be concluded that entrepreneurship helped many women to enhance their level of empowerment.

Table 3 Capacity to Mobilise Funds by Sample Respondents

Source of fund	Manufacturing		Service		Total	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
Own	13 (18.06)	6 (8.11)	10 (15.15)	11 (13.25)	23 (16.67)	17 (10.83)

Family	9 (12.50)	14 (18.92)	27 (40.91)	16 (19.28)	36 (26.09)	30 (19.11)
Bank Loan	29 (40.28)	39 (52.70)	16 (24.24)	47 (56.63)	45 (32.61)	86 (54.78)
Loans from friends	14 (19.44)	7 (9.46)	3 (4.54)	5 (6.02)	17 (12.32)	12 (7.64)
Money lenders	3 (4.17)	5 (6.76)	5 (7.58)	2 (2.41)	8 (5.81)	7 (4.46)
Others	4 (5.55)	3 (4.05)	5 (7.58)	2 (2.41)	9 (6.52)	5 (3.19)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate the percentage to total.

Source: Sample survey.

Family Income

Economic independence is essential to ensure women empowerment. Women entrepreneurship provides employment to women. It enhances the earnings of women, resulting in their economic independence. Women entrepreneurship substantially contributes to their empowerment through the provision of earnings. Women entrepreneurs were reluctant to reveal the actual increase in the family income due to various reasons. A look at the Table 4 shows that there is a substantial increase in the

Table 4 Increase in the Family Income of Sample Women Entrepreneurs

Change	Manufacturing		Service		Total	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
Substantial increase	41 (56.94)	34 (45.95)	31 (46.97)	29 (34.97)	72 (52.17)	63 (40.13)
Normal increase	22 (30.56)	29 (39.19)	31 (46.97)	39 (46.99)	53 (38.41)	68 (43.31)
No change	9 (12.50)	11 (14.86)	4 (6.06)	15 (18.07)	13 (9.42)	26 (16.56)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate the percentage to total

Source: Sample survey.

family income of 56.94 per cent of urban and 45.95 percent of rural entrepreneurs engaged in manufacturing. There is a normal increase in 30.56 per cent of urban and 39.19 per cent of rural families. In the rest of cases, income remained unchanged. The family income of 46.97 per cent of urban and 34.97 per cent of rural entrepreneurs engaged in service units has increased remarkably. The increase was normal in the case of 46.97 per cent of urban respondents and 46.99 per cent of in the case of their rural counterparts. In the rest of the cases, it remained static. When all the samples are put together, the enhancement is substantial in 52.17 per cent of urban and 40.13 per cent of rural households. A contrary picture emerges with regard to normal and no increase categories. There is no significant difference in the increase between manufacturing and service units. This is based on the fact that the calculated value of chi-square is 5.592, which is less than the table value of 5.991 at 5 percent level and 2 d.f. It can be clearly stated that women empowerment had indeed taken place since the income of respondents has gone up due to entrepreneurship.

Expenditure on Health and Nutritional Diet

The expenditure pattern shows the style of using funds for day to day activities. Health care is vital as it affects attitude towards family and social status. Women empowerment includes the expenditure on nutritional diet of the family. From personal interaction with the sample women entrepreneur respondents, it is observed that there is substantial increase in the expenditure on nutritional diet after undertaking entrepreneurship.

Standard of Living

Earnings may reflect the standard of living of entrepreneurs. The standard of living is measured by the comforts enjoyed in living. It can be observed from Table 5 that 129 families of entrepreneurs have acquired television sets after getting into

Table 5 Possession of Household Articles and Vehicles by Select Women Entrepreneurs

Possession	Before entering Entrepreneurship	After entering Entrepreneurship	Increase	% of increase
Television	163	292	129	79.14
Mixie/grinder	190	290	100	52.63
Refrigerator	98	153	55	56.13
Washing machine	18	106	88	488.89
Moped	43	214	171	397.67
Motor cycle/Scooter	12	63	51	425
Car/Van	16	41	25	156.25

Source: Sample Survey

entrepreneurship; and those who acquired mixie/grinder are 100, refrigerator 55 and washing machine 88. With regard to vehicles, 171 purchased mopeds, 51 motor cycle/scooters and 25 car/van. It can be concluded that there is a considerable increase in the possession of comfort articles and vehicles after setting up an industrial venture by women entrepreneurs.

Decision-Making

Decision making ability is the culmination of knowledge, skills and confidence, which leads to empowerment. It is pertinent to ascertain the extent to which decisions taken by women are accepted by family members. Women entrepreneurs take business decisions as well as decisions on family matters. Empowerment of women can take place if they are allowed to take decisions on their own. It may be gauged from Table 6 that in the manufacturing sector, 16.67 per cent of urban and 18.92 per cent of rural entrepreneurs discuss with others and make group decisions; 58.33 per cent of urban and 50.00 per cent of rural respondents discuss with others but take decisions on their own; and the rest do not discuss with others but take their own decisions. In the service sector, 16.67 per cent of urban and 22.89 per cent of rural entrepreneurs discuss with others and make group decisions; 42.42 per cent of urban and 40.96 per cent of rural entrepreneurs discuss with others but take their

Table 6 Methods of Business Decision Making Among Respondents

Method	Manufacturing		Service		Total	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
Discuss with others, make group decision	12 (16.67)	14 (18.92)	11 (16.67)	19 (22.89)	23 (16.67)	33 (21.02)
Discuss with others, but take own decision	42 (58.33)	37 (50.00)	28 (42.42)	34 (40.96)	70 (50.22)	71 (45.22)
Own decision without discussion	18 (25.00)	31 (31.08)	27 (40.91)	30 (36.15)	45 (32.61)	53 (33.76)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate the percentage to total

Source: Sample survey

own decisions; and the remaining do not discuss with others but take their own decisions. On the whole, 18.98 per cent discuss with others and make group decisions; 47.80 per cent discuss with others but take their own decisions; and the rest do not discuss with others but take own decisions. It is evident from what is stated earlier that empowerment is more in manufacturing units as compared to service units. Further, it is higher among urban entrepreneurs in comparison with rural entrepreneurs. It can be further observed that over two-thirds of entrepreneurs take decisions on their own. This is a clear proof that the increasing decision making competencies of women results in greater empowerment of women.

In the case of manufacturing activity, 30.56 percent of urban and 39.19 per cent of rural entrepreneurs reported that their family members always accept their decisions; 40.56 percent of urban and 24.32 per cent of rural respondents reported that their families rarely accepted their decisions; and the remaining revealed that their decisions are not accepted by family members. (see Table 7) As regards the service sector, the majority of urban and rural entrepreneurs opined that their decisions are rarely accepted by family members. As a whole, 32.20 per cent of entrepreneurs reported that their decisions are always accepted; 44.07 per.

Table 7 Acceptance of Respondents' Decisions by Family Members

Response	Manufacturing		Service		Total	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
Always accept	22 (30.56)	29 (39.19)	17 (25.76)	27 (32.53)	39 (28.26)	56 (35.67)
Rarely accept	31 (40.56)	18 (24.32)	36 (54.54)	45 (54.22)	67 (48.55)	63 (40.13)
Not accept	19 (26.39)	27 (36.49)	13 (19.70)	11 (11.25)	32 (23.19)	38 (24.20)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate the percentage to total

Source: Sample survey

cent said that their decisions are rarely accepted; and the rest expressed the view that their family members did not accept their decisions. It may hence, be concluded that a majority of the households accept the decisions of entrepreneurs either always or at least occasionally. It clearly points to the existing and enhancing women empowerment. At the macro-level, empowerment is more among rural entrepreneurs as against their urban counter parts. Empowerment is higher in the service sector than in the manufacturing sector.

Group Cohesiveness

Group cohesiveness is vital for women empowerment. Women join groups to achieve their objectives. Group cohesiveness among women entrepreneurs can be studied through joint representation and participation in social activities. Women entrepreneurs experience either business or social problems. They have to represent their grievances to the authorities concerned. For redress of their grievances, 70.83 per cent of urban and 56.76 per cent of rural entrepreneurs from manufacturing sector take part in-group representations (see Table 8). In service units, 42.42 percent of urban and 40.96 per cent of rural respondents adopt group representations method. When both categories are put together, 57.25 per cent of urban and 48.41 per cent of rural entrepreneurs take part in group representations and the rest do not associate with group representations. It may be inferred that group representations are more among entrepreneurs belonging to manufacturing activities than those of service sector. A similar trend exists in urban households.

Table 8 Group Representation for Grievance Redressal

Response	Manufacturing		Service		Total	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
Take part in group Representations	51 (70.88)	42 (56.76)	28 (42.42)	34 (40.96)	79 (57.25)	76 (48.41)
Do not take part in group representations	21 (29.17)	32 (43.24)	38 (57.58)	49 (59.04)	59 (42.75)	81 (51.59)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate the percentage to total

Source: Sample survey

Homemakers initially participate in social activities to improve the quality of life of their family through using healthy food and environmentally safe products. Once they participate, they develop a sense of confidence and fulfillment and look beyond their existence within their families. To assess the level of participation in social activities, sample women entrepreneurs were asked as to whether, after becoming entrepreneurs, did they join club/society, participate in social, political or religious gatherings and involve in environmental protection activities. Of the 295 respondents, 85 rural and 99 urban enrolled

Table 9 Participation of Respondents in Social Activities

Social Activities	Manufacturing		Service		Total	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
Membership in club/society	43	48	56	37	99	85
Participation in social, political and religious gatherings	52	57	56	54	108	111
Involvement in environment protection activities	60	47	69	45	129	92

Source: Sample Survey

Themselves in welfare clubs and social organizations (see table 9). Among the sample women entrepreneur respondents, 108 and 111 urban and rural respectively participated in social, political and religious gatherings. Those involved in environmental protection activities are 129 and 92 from urban and rural areas respectively. It can be summed up that enrolment of women in welfare clubs, religious, political and social gatherings and environmental protection activities is the result of entrepreneurship. The participation of women entrepreneurs in all the activities referred to is clearly, an outcome of their empowerment.

Self-confidence

Self-confidence is necessary to meet the critical situations of life courageously. All the respondents, without any exception, have emphatically stated that their level of self-confidence has increased after becoming entrepreneurs. Table 10 shows that a majority of women entrepreneurs have occasionally enforced strict control and discipline in their units. Over 43 per cent of women entrepreneurs usually control their family members. Nearly 79 percent of women entrepreneurs travel alone. Around 68 percent of women entrepreneurs spend on their own without consulting others. More than half of the respondents

Table 10 Assessment of Self-confidence Level Among Entrepreneurs

Practices	Usually	Occasionally	Never	Total
Do you have strict control over discipline at your work place?	101 (34.24)	158 (53.7)	36 (12.20)	295 (100)
Do you control your family members in their usual activities	128 (43.39)	65 (22.03)	102 (34.58)	295 (100)
Do you travel alone without the assistance of family members?	233 (78.98)	47 (15.93)	15 (5.09)	295 (100)
Do you spend on your own without consulting others?	200 (67.80)	32 (10.89)	63 (21.35)	295 (100)
Do you represent to Authorities directly?	125 (42.37)	149 (50.51)	21 (7.12)	295 (100)
Do you counsel family members and workers?	121 (41.02)	161 (54.58)	13 (4.40)	295 (100)
Do you give directions to family members and workers in social or economical aspects?	170 (57.63)	78 (26.44)	47 (15.963)	295 (100)

Note: Figures in parentheses indicate the percentage to total.

Source: Sample survey.

Occasionally represent the authorities directly; nearly 55 percent of entrepreneurs occasionally counsel their family members and workers. Majority entrepreneurs usually give directions to their family members and workers. Weights assigned to understand the prominent parameters of women empowerment include usually:+2, occasionally:+1; never:0. It is found that the pattern of travelling is maximum among women entrepreneurs. Next is spending on their own. The third one is giving directions on social and economic matters. The fourth parameter is counselling and the fifth one is direct representation to authorities. These activities, prima facie, reflect the growing empowerment of women entrepreneurs.

Conclusion

Entrepreneurship has led to significant advancement in the educational status of both urban and rural women entrepreneurs and is the highest in manufacturing sector. Majority of the respondents got trained technically and it is significantly evident in manufacturing sector. Almost two-thirds of women entrepreneurs mobilized required funds for their entrepreneurs independently. It demonstrates that entrepreneurship is the most powerful means of empowering women. Entrepreneurship has contributed to the substantial increase in the income level of respondents and it is more pronounced in urban women entrepreneurs than in rural. Women entrepreneurs have spent considerable amounts on nutritional diet. After becoming entrepreneurs, the standards of living of women improved a lot. It is found that empowerment through decision-making is

more in service units as compared to manufacturing. Majority of respondents take part in-group representations. More than two thirds of women entrepreneurs participate in welfare clubs, political, social and religious gatherings and environment protection activities. After becoming entrepreneurs, self-confidence of respondents has increased significantly. Entrepreneurial climate, technological changes, business problems, escalating work stress search for new opportunities and the like force women entrepreneurs to become bold, self-confident and develop abilities to face any situation, whatever may be its magnitude. Methodical decision-making and positive attitude towards entrepreneurship will result in radical changes in the life style of women and, in turn, creates a society, which will acknowledge the reality of women empowerment.

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